

GRAMMATICAL STUDY OF THE STRUCTURE AND FORMATION OF IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT: In this article, we describe the grammatical study of the structure and formation of idioms in the English language and the history of their origin, as well as their typological changes.

KEY WORDS: phraseological units, idioms, formation, grammatical study, structure, language phenomena.

INTRODUCTION: Phraseological units in both oral and written form of the national literary language; are language phenomena widely used in spoken and written speech. Dictionary of the language one of the constituent units is phraseology.

Phraseologisms language appears in speech as a unit. They are impressive and colorful speech ensures that. Phraseological units of a people who speak a certain language reflects the richness of the cultural language and is unique to their worldview helps reveal the features. Phraseologisms in each language learning are important and fun. This article is in English translation of idiomatic expressions and attention to their semantic features directed.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: Phraseological expressions are unique to a language, regardless of the form in which they are used seems to have a norm. The same norm applies from one language to another makes it difficult to pass. Phraseological phrases are usually two or more words as a result of their combinations, their appearance is in word combinations looks like. There are even such phraseologisms and combinations of words that can be used as a phrase and it is not easy to differentiate in the compound case. This means that word combinations denotative, and phraseologisms acquire a connotative character and them must be distinguished from the context. So, any combination of words is not considered phraseology. They are complex in terms of structure and meaning, is a multifaceted linguistic phenomenon with certain norms and specific features.

The place and role of the national language in the formation of expressions has been great since time immemorial. Actually in the vernacular created phrases gradually entered the literary language through artistic works.

Phraseologisms are interesting in all languages because of their literal translation impossible to do and understand. Phraseological combinations enliven the language, them although difficult to develop, they are polished and have a special place in the language. Often they are related to the culture and history of the country. Just like that Uzbek translation of some English idiomatic phrases with characteristics. [1.95]

Let's see through:

- 1) The apple of your eye - cute, beloved
- 2) Go bananas - to get angry, get angry

- 3) A bite at the cherry - to achieve success
- 4) Not give a fig - unimportant
- 5) Apples and oranges are different from each other
- 6) Lemon - useless
- 7) As red as a cherry - red
- 8) Cherry-pick - the most necessary, important
- 9) The cherry on the cake – a perfect ending

Among these expressions, only some have equivalents in other languages we can see that there is. For example: The apple never falls far from the tree – an apple falls under an apple; the idiom is also available in the Uzbek language. Besides in Italian there is an expression with the same meaning: Una mela non cade lontana dall'albero¹. [4.63]

- In literal translation, "the apple does not fall far from the tree" In the case of the phrase, "Apples fall under apples"; from the child's parents means that it does not differ much, it is often used in a negative sense. For example: "Pensavo che Mario fosse diverso da suo padre e invece è cattivo come lui" "Eh, purtroppo una mela non cade lontana dall'albero" - I thought he didn't look like Mario's father, but he does unfortunately, children always look like their parents.

The vocabulary of any language is not only about creating new words, maybe, because of expressions, stable word combinations, both in terms of quantity and quality becomes richer in terms of With the "world" with such stable compounds the science involved is the science of phraseology. Phraseology is the study of phrases and this term was used by E.D. Polivanov in 1928: I refer to morphology syntax is related to lexis to use the term "phraseology" as a special science dealing with relations I found it necessary. [2.74]

The change of the meaning of fixed combinations in the language is the result of a deeper study and familiarity with the events in the world, human thinking it is created due to the development of abilities. Technology and science growth, the owner of the language, the creator of the people with the neighboring countries from the same language as a result of being in contact, increasing trade with them the language becomes richer due to the number of words transferred to the second language that is why the change of the meanings of fixed combinations in the language together with the history of the society it will be necessary to check.

It is known that people give names to objects according to their important characteristics. They give that a specific object has not one, but several characters possible. [4.85] That's why some people look at a certain object, looking at one of its signs, and others may give names based on other characteristics. So, names are characteristic of the object or things, not by themselves it is named according to its characteristics, that is, according to its most important aspects. Such names are formed through the transfer of the meanings of stable compounds will come. For example, Koklam compared to spring or Amir Temur. The naming of Sakhirqiran words is also a process that took place in this way can be understood. It is clear from this that the meaning of stable compounds objects is named and their important features are revealed Paying attention to the process is the first priority.

It turned out that any name by another name, that is, things it can be replaced with a name that does not match the feature or character it's not. Something between the noun replaced or referred to and the subject the connection must be close. At the same time, the

name of the changed thing the reader or listener is clear about the important, significant aspect, feature imagination should be generated. Then it will have a real name.

For example, when "white gold" is said, no one understands the precious metal, everyone knows that it is cotton. Cotton is the subject name. This subject a noun, that is, a descriptive expression with the characteristics of this subject happens and appears as his second name. Everyone in the world the words in the vocabulary of languages have a figurative meaning in addition to their meaning serves to name another object or event. It should also be said that the meaning of stable compounds is shifting or change is not an accidental point, but it is a necessity of life. Because this is your language the phenomenon is closely related to various aspects of life, its development depends. [3.109]

The transfer of the meaning of a stable combination is the very existence of a language system is one of its characteristic features. The proper use of these units is functional to be in an adequate form, that is, to combine unit means: these units are formed by speakers in a certain space and time; from the point of view of the presence of language: language is social psychophysiological connecting sounds with meaning from the sound matter of group skills is a product of formation of units through; from a semiotic point of view: language is system of signs, that is, representing things and objects in material existence is a set of special characters that exist outside of themselves has the characteristic of meaning something; in terms of information theory: language, it is a code through which semantic information is encoded.

CONCLUSION: Showing different types of phraseological equivalents in the languages being compared serves to learn a foreign language and to learn translation, the equivalents themselves if it is, it is shown in bilingual dictionaries. Comparison of specific, concrete phraseological units helps to collect material in various directions: theory of translation, theory of phraseography and comparative-typological studies. On the basis of these concrete the object of comprehensive study lies between phraseological units if there is no correspondence, there will be a complete difference between the phraseological units.

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